

Synthesis of 2-Thio- Δ^4 -Thiazolines as Possible Fungicides

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Seven ammonium dithio-carbamates prepared from aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline, *p*-iodoaniline, α -naphthylamine and β -naphthylamine have been condensed with twelve different (aliphatic, aromatic and alicyclic) ketones, both saturated and unsaturated, in the presence of bromine to yield 2-thio-3,4,5-substituted- Δ^4 -thiazolines. These thiazolines have been assayed for their fungicidal activity and an attempt has been made to establish a relationship between fungicidal activity and chemical structure.

THE versatility of thiazoles and their derivatives is demonstrated by the fact that some of these compounds possess antimalarial¹, anthelmintic², antifungal^{3,4}, antibacterial⁵, antispasmodic⁶, and anti-tubercular⁷ activities. Some more uses of such compounds are as local anaesthetic⁸, antiradiation drugs⁹, antiviral¹⁰, and antiprotozoal agents¹¹, and above all as vulcanisation accelerators¹² in the rubber industry.

The present work, records the synthesis of thiazoline compounds by reacting ketones with the freshly prepared dithio-carbamates using bromine as the condensing agent. This method obviates the use of haloketones which are not available easily. The versatility of the present method rests on the fact that by using various dithiocarbamates and different ketones, a large number of thiazolines can be synthesized having desired substituents at 3,4 and 5-positions of the thiazoline nucleus^{13,14}. The presence of a thio-group as well as halogens in the thiazoline compounds is expected to increase their fungicidal property¹⁵. In this communication, a comparative evaluation of the fungicidal activity of a large number of 2-thio-thiazolines having different substituents at 3,4 and 5-positions of the thiazoline nucleus has been made with the object of establishing a relationship between chemical structure and fungicidal activity.

Results and Discussion

From a study of the fungicidal activity given in Table 1, it will be observed that the thiazoline compounds possess good fungicidal property. Analysis of the fungicidal action shows that the introduction of the thio-group in the thiazoline nucleus at 2-position does not enhance the fungicidal activity and the substitution of N-R group by a thio-group decreases the fungicidal activity⁸.

Of the seven series of compounds tested, the series having a naphthalene nucleus attached at N₃-position

is the most active, and the other of fungicidal activity is as follows :

Substituents at C₄-position of the thiazoline nucleus have very little influence over the activity. However, the aromatic substituent is more effective than the aliphatic ones.

If the aromatic substituents carry a halogen or phenolic group, the activity is enhanced in the following order :

Some of these compounds (numbered 52 to 60 in Table 1) which show maximum antifungal activity against *Piricularia oryzae* (Cav.) were also tested against *Helminthosporium oryzae*. It is observed that the fungicidal effect of these compounds is stronger towards *Piricularia oryzae* (Cav.) than *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

These compounds in general show stronger fungicidal activity towards *Piricularia Oryzae* (Cav.) than towards *Carrularia lunata* or *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

Experimental

(a) 2-Thio-3,4-diphenyl- Δ^4 -thiazoline : To a mixture of acetophenone (3 g.) and absolute alcohol (15 ml) in a dry conical flask was added gradually a mixture of bromine (4 g) and absolute alcohol (15 ml.) under stirring. Freshly prepared phenyl ammonium dithiocarbamate¹⁶ (4.7 g) was then added to the above acetophenone-bromine mixture and refluxed for 18 hrs. on a steam bath. Excess of alcohol was removed by distillation and the residue triturated with ether. After extraction with ether several times to remove the unreacted ketone and bromine which make the

TABLE I. ANALYTICAL AND FUNGICIDAL RESULTS OF 2-THIO- Δ^4 -THIAZOLINES

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	S(%)		Fungicidal Results	
						Found	Calc.	Ger. at 10 p.p.m. (%)	Test Fungus
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	135	80	23.60	23.80	70	<i>Carvularia Lunata</i>
2.	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃ -	H	145	75	31.10	30.91	58	"
3.	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃ -	COO-C ₂ H ₅ -	190	50	23.10	22.93	50	"
4.	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃ -	CH ₃ -	165	70	28.51	28.96	60	"
5.	C ₆ H ₅ -	4 : 5-Tetra-methylene		178	80	25.25	25.51	70	"
6.	C ₆ H ₅ -	(CH ₃) ₂ -CH-CH ₂ -	H	230	72	25.52	25.70	60	"
7.	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	188	80	21.34	21.55	60	"
8.	C ₆ H ₅ -	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	141	70	18.06	18.39	50	"
9.	C ₆ H ₅ -	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	H	250	65	22.27	22.61	40	"
10.	C ₆ H ₅ -	(p)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	134	60	21.28	21.40	68	"
11.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	130	70	22.28	22.61	18	<i>Piricularia Oryzae (Cav)</i>
12.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	H	110	75	28.58	28.96	25	"
13.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	CH ₃ -	122	70	26.57	27.23	18	"
14.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	(o)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	150	60	21.00	21.43	12	"
15.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	155	65	21.12	21.43	18	"
16.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	130	65	21.12	20.40	18	"
17.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	118	60	19.81	20.16	14	"
18.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	105	70	17.82	17.68	20	"
19.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	170	60	21.25	20.58	18	"
20.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₄ -	H	125	75	20.85	21.09	20	<i>Carvularia Lunata</i>
21.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	H	113	65	26.25	26.50	60	"
22.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	(CH ₃) ₂ -CH-CH ₂ -	H	170	72	22.34	22.57	75	"
23.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	4 : 5-Tetra-methylene		115	75	22.45	22.73	76	"
24.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	COO-C ₂ H ₅ -	195	70	20.16	20.41	50	"
25.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	169	70	16.25	16.73	40	"
26.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	108	80	19.12	19.36	60	"
27.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	CH ₃ -	125	65	24.58	25.05	72	"
28.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	H	190	85	21.85	22.37	32	<i>Piricularia Oryzae (Cav)</i>
29.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	210	75	17.62	18.39	20	"
30.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	COOC ₂ H ₅ -	160	60	17.16	17.87	12	"
31.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	CH ₃ -	177	75	20.70	21.33	12	"
32.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	4 : 5-Tetra-methylene		195	65	19.16	19.63	30	"
33.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	(CH ₃) ₂ -CH-CH ₂ -	H	151	72	19.02	19.54	20	"
34.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	193	68	16.42	16.73	15	"
35.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	208	70	16.53	16.93	17	"
36.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	(o)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	198	75	17.70	17.58	30	"
37.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	201	65	15.36	15.78	12	"
38.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	188	70	17.13	17.58	37	"
39.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	204	75	16.76	17.12	31	"
40.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	H	170	75	18.64	19.23	40	"
41.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	169	68	15.71	16.20	37	"
42.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	COOC ₂ H ₅ -	148	70	15.26	15.81	28	"
43.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -	CH ₃ -	241	65	17.92	18.42	25	"
44.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	4 : 5-Tetra-methylene		145	72	16.66	17.16	40	"
45.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	(CH ₃) ₂ -CH-CH ₂ -	H	192	65	16.57	17.07	20	"
46.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	199	75	14.38	14.90	25	"
47.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	214	75	14.47	15.06	32	"
48.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	179	64	13.52	14.13	36	"
49.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃ -CH ₂ -	H	174	72	13.12	13.50	22	"
50.	(p)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	(p)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	188	76	15.08	15.57	42	"

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TABLE I (Contd.)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	S(%)		Fungicidal Results	
						Found	Calc.	Ger. at 10 p.p.m. (%)	Test Fungus
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
51.	(<i>p</i>)I-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	196	74	14.72	15.13	43	"
52.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	CH ₃ -	H	78	62	24.70	24.90	11 *24	<i>Piricularia Oryzae</i> (Cav)
53.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	98	60	20.10	20.06	10 *22	"
54.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	CH ₃ -	COO.C ₂ H ₅ -	87	62	19.50	19.45	15 *28	"
55.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	(CH ₃) ₂ -CH-CH ₂ -	H	160	63	21.20	21.40	18 *30	"
56.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	(<i>p</i>)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	100	65	16.10	16.08	10 *20	"
57.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	(<i>p</i>)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	95	63	18.40	18.34	14 *30	"
58.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	(<i>p</i>)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	92	63	19.00	19.10	16 *30	"
59.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	(<i>p</i>)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	90	65	17.10	16.98	12 *25	"
60.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	CH ₂ -CH ₂ - CH ₃ -	CH ₃ -	168	62	23.40	23.61	12 *25	"
61.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	92	72	20.18	20.06	8	"
62.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	CH ₃ -	H	102	65	24.72	24.90	9	"
63.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	CH ₃ -	CH ₃ -	98	62	23.26	23.61	12	"
64.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	CH ₃ -	COO C ₂ H ₅ -	165	55	19.26	19.45	16	"
65.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	105	65	18.12	18.44	10	"
66.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	(<i>o</i>)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	140	60	18.87	19.10	12	"
67.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	(<i>p</i>)OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	145	60	18.78	19.10	12	"
68.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	(<i>p</i>)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	125	70	18.31	18.10	13	"
69.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	(CH ₃) ₂ -CH-CH ₂ -	H	175	60	21.14	21.40	16	"

* % of germination at 10 p.p.m. when *Helminthosporium Oryzae* was used as the test fungus.

product gummy, the residue was washed with water to remove the unreacted dithio-carbamate and then treated with liquor ammonia to liberate the free base. It was filtered and finally crystallised from ethanol; yield 80% m.p. 135° (Found: N, 5.08; S, 23.60, C₁₅H₁₁NS₂ requires N, 5.20; S, 23.80%).

The melting points, % yields and analytical data of other 2-thio- Δ^4 -thiazolines are reported in Table I.

(b) *Assay of the fungicidal activity*: The fungicidal activity was determined following the method of Montgomery and Moore¹⁷ with slight modifications, using *Piricularia oryzae* (Cav.), *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Carvularia lunata* as the test fungi. The fungicidal assay, based on % of germination at 10 p.p.m., is given in Table I. The spores were kept with fungicides at different concentrations for 24 hrs.

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